

OneN: Guided Attention for Natively-Explainable Anomaly Detection

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Abstract

In industrial computer vision applications, anomaly detection (AD) is a critical task for ensuring product quality and system reliability. However, many existing AD systems follow a modular design that decouples classification from detection and localization tasks. Although this separation simplifies model development, it often limits generalizability and reduces practical effectiveness in real-world scenarios. Deep neural networks offer strong potential for unified solutions. Nonetheless, most current approaches still treat detection, localization and classification as separate components, hindering the development of more integrated and efficient AD pipelines. To bridge this gap, we propose OneN (One Network), a unified architecture that performs detection, localization, and classification within a single framework. Our approach distills knowledge from a high-capacity convolutional neural network (CNN) into an attention-based architecture trained under varying levels of supervision. The resulting attention maps act as interpretable pseudo-segmentation masks, enabling accurate localization of anomalous regions. To further enhance localization quality, we introduce a progressive focal loss that guides attention maps at each layer to focus on critical features. We validate our method through extensive experiments on both standardized and custom-defined industrial benchmarks. Even under weak supervision, it improves performance, reduces annotation effort, and facilitates scalable deployment in industrial environments.

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1 Introduction

Advanced manufacturing is increasingly adopting artificial intelligence (AI) to enhance production processes, ensure product quality, and support the maintenance of operational equipment [1]. Among its many applications, AI is being leveraged to predict machine faults (predictive maintenance) [2], detect anomalies in sensor data (anomaly detection) [3], and optimize production efficiency (process optimization) [4].

Vision-based automated defect detection systems [3] represent a key application area, targeting both *structural* anomalies (*e.g.*, physical damages) and *logical* anomalies (*e.g.*, omissions or misplacements). In this context, three core tasks are typically addressed: detection, localization and classification. Each serves a distinct purpose within automated inspection systems and is often implemented using specialized neural network architectures [5]. Detection focuses on establishing whether an image contains an anomaly, without specifying its exact location or type. This is typically framed as a binary classification problem (normal vs. anomalous), where global image-level features are extracted to make a decision. While classification networks can be adapted for detection, autoencoders (*e.g.*, U-Net [6]) are typically employed to generate anomaly heatmaps, which can then be thresholded to produce an image-level anomaly score. The key question in detection is “*Is this image anomalous?*”. Localization, instead, aims to identify the specific regions within an image that correspond to an anomaly, providing a pixel-wise defect segmentation. This task requires a network able to predict an anomaly mask to highlight the exact spatial extent of the defect. Localization is essential in applications where interpretability is crucial, such as industrial quality control [1]. The key question addressed by localization is “*Where is the anomaly in the image?*”. Finally, classification refers to assigning a label to an input image from a predefined set of categories, such as different types of defects in an industrial setting (*e.g.*, scratch, hole, or a generic damaged label). A classification network, such as a ResNet model [7], is often used to learn features that help discriminate normal from abnormal categories. In this case, the main question addressed is “*What type of anomaly is present?*”.

Conventional techniques [8] often lack robustness and accuracy, prompting the development of supervised [9, 10] and unsupervised [11, 12, 13] meth-

35 ods that offer substantial improvements. Multi-class unified anomaly de-
36 tection (MUAD) approaches [14] further enhance scalability by generalizing
37 across multiple classes instead of relying on separate models. This is achieved
38 by capturing shared semantic patterns among categories [15, 16, 17]. How-
39 ever, they are typically designed to handle a single task at a time and of-
40 ten exhibit a significant performance degradation under distribution shifts.
41 Consequently, multiple specialized models are frequently required, resulting
42 in increased computational overhead and inefficiencies in deployment. For
43 example, Hu *et al.* [5] employ a supervised framework composed of multiple
44 distinct networks to address each task individually.

45 As a potential remedy, explainable AI (XAI) techniques [18] provide in-
46 sights into neural network decisions and can facilitate both detection and
47 localization within a unified framework. More specifically, visual explana-
48 tion methods analyze internal network representations to identify image re-
49 gions that are most influential for a given prediction. CAM-based tech-
50 niques [19, 20, 21], for example, generate class activation maps, often guided
51 by gradients, that highlight salient features contributing to a model’s out-
52 put. While these approaches were initially conceived for CNNs, attention-
53 based mechanisms such as self-attention in Vision Transformers (ViTs) [22]
54 have shown promise in capturing similarly informative patterns [23, 22, 24].
55 Despite their advantages, significant challenges persist in jointly enhancing
56 explainability and anomaly detection performance. ViT-based models gener-
57 ate informative attention maps and achieve strong classification performance;
58 however, their adoption in industrial settings remains limited for two key rea-
59 sons: *(i)* self-attention mechanisms do not inherently localize anomalous re-
60 gions, and *(ii)* their high computational requirements make them unsuitable
61 for low-latency, energy-constrained environments [24]. To overcome these
62 limitations, we propose a family of attention-based models tailored to di-
63 verse industrial requirements, along with a progressive guidance mechanism
64 for self-attention that reduces dependence on heavy supervision, which is
65 often necessary in prior methods [10, 5].

66 Knowledge distillation (KD) has been employed to improve the perfor-
67 mance of compact models with limited representational capacity, offering so-
68 lutions that balance accuracy with fast inference and low resource consump-
69 tion, which are key priorities in industrial applications. [25, 26]. Traditional
70 KD approaches [27] are typically designed for homogeneous architectures,
71 such as CNN-to-CNN or Transformer-to-Transformer, where representation
72 spaces are aligned. A common technique, logits-matching, is simple but

73 may degrade student performance when teacher predictions are uncertain or
74 noisy [28]. Distillation between heterogeneous architectures, like CNNs and
75 ViTs, introduces additional challenges. CNNs gradually expand the recep-
76 tive field through feature downsampling and spatial convolutions, whereas
77 ViTs achieve a global receptive field immediately via self-attention. Their
78 block structures also differ, CNNs are stage-specific, while ViTs use uniform
79 blocks. Furthermore, CNNs typically use batch or group normalization, while
80 ViTs rely on layer normalization, making feature or relation alignment more
81 difficult. For these reasons, the application of KD is often limited to specific
82 architectures and industrial tasks [29].

83 To address these challenges, this work proposes a unified framework that
84 combines classification, detection, and localization into a single pipeline. Our
85 approach employs KD to transfer knowledge from a high-capacity network
86 to an attention-based architecture, enabling it to classify both normal and
87 defective samples while using the ViT’s attention maps to detect anomalies
88 and generate segmentation masks. Given the strong performance of convolu-
89 tional neural networks on small-scale datasets, we use a CNN as the teacher.
90 We then distill knowledge into the student model using synthetic data gen-
91 erated by state-of-the-art AD generative models. To enhance localization
92 performance when segmentation masks are available, we introduce a novel
93 progressive masking mechanism during training. In this regard, we leverage
94 the student’s self-attention by including synthetic masks, either directly or by
95 converting them into weakly annotated bounding boxes, which are easier to
96 collect. By integrating classification, detection, and localization with weakly
97 annotated mask supervision and adaptable architectures, the approach ef-
98 fectively addresses diverse industrial requirements. It also offers a practical
99 trade-off between annotation cost and performance.

100 We summarize our main contributions as follows:

- 101 • We propose OneN, a unified framework based on KD that transfers
102 knowledge from a convolutional teacher network to a ViT-based stu-
103 dent, enabling a single model to jointly perform detection, localization
104 and classification tasks.
- 105 • We introduce a progressive focal loss mechanism that guides both shal-
106 low and deeper attention layers to effectively localize structural anoma-
107 lies.
- 108 • We investigate the use of synthetic images generated by diffusion-based

109 models for anomaly detection, and define multiple evaluation protocols
110 and input settings to reflect the diverse requirements of real-world in-
111 dustrial production lines. We compare our approach against multiple
112 architectures currently used in such settings.

- 113 • We demonstrate that attention maps from a ViT model can be effec-
114 tively used to detect anomalies without requiring additional networks
115 or decoupling classification and detection/localization tasks. Our ap-
116 proach also generalizes well across various input configurations and in-
117 dustrial scenarios. Furthermore, we show that weak supervision (*e.g.*,
118 bounding boxes) remains effective, significantly reducing annotation
119 cost while maintaining competitive performance.

120 The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses
121 related work. Section 3 presents our proposed model, based on KD and
122 attention maps to detect anomalies using one architecture. Section 4 presents
123 the main input settings and our results, along with a comprehensive analysis
124 of the effectiveness of synthetic data for anomaly detection. Finally, Section 5
125 concludes the paper and discusses possible future research directions.

126 2. Related Work

127 Anomaly detection in industrial contexts aims to identify out-of-distribution
128 (OOD) samples, wherein anomalous instances show statistical properties that
129 deviate from the distribution of the available normal data [30, 31]. Given
130 the relative ease of collecting normal samples, unsupervised methods have
131 been developed to localize anomalies exclusively based on normal data dis-
132 tributions [32, 33]. Distribution-based approaches [34, 35] enhance feature
133 alignment by leveraging pre-estimated statistical representations or memory
134 banks. Patch-based techniques [36, 37], which perform fine-grained analyses
135 at the patch level, have demonstrated improved sensitivity to subtle defects.
136 Furthermore, recent advances have introduced multi-modal frameworks that
137 integrate visual and linguistic modalities, offering enriched semantic under-
138 standing for anomaly detection [38, 39, 40]. Although these methods demon-
139 strate strong performance in detecting anomalies, they continue to face sig-
140 nificant challenges in meeting industrial requirements, particularly in terms
141 of latency and efficiency [41, 42].

142 In the following, we provide a detailed overview of the main works related to
143 our proposed approach.

144 *2.1. Knowledge Distillation*

145 Knowledge Distillation (KD) is widely employed to transfer learned knowl-
146 edge from a large, well-performing teacher model to a compact student net-
147 work. While logit-based KD is straightforward methodology to apply [27],
148 feature-based distillation between heterogeneous architectures, especially from
149 CNNs to Vision Transformers, remains challenging due to structural mis-
150 matches.

151 Touvron *et al.* [24] introduce a distillation token into the ViT architecture
152 and train it using hard-label distillation, achieving performance on par with
153 CNNs on mid-sized datasets while improving throughput. However, this ap-
154 proach benefits more from CNN-based teachers due to their inductive biases.
155 Yang *et al.* [43] demonstrate that direct feature alignment between CNNs
156 and ViTs degrades performance and propose a hybrid strategy: mimick-
157 ing shallow features and employing a generative approach for deeper layers.
158 TinyViT [44] defines a logit-based KD strategy for compressing large ViTs
159 using sparse soft labels and constrained local search across embedding size,
160 block depth, and channel count. Kang *et al.* [45] improve KD by aligning
161 both the classification token and its attention maps to patches, although their
162 method requires manual layer selection. Zheng *et al.* [46] address the CNN-
163 to-ViT gap by using global average pooling and multi-head self-attention to
164 render CNN features compatible with ViTs. Lin *et al.* [47] invert the di-
165 rection, distilling from ViTs to CNNs via a teacher collaboration strategy
166 that combines ViT- and CNN-based guidance using cross-attention. OFA-
167 KD [28] aligns logits and early-exit branches across heterogeneous models,
168 using adaptive weights to prevent learning from less confident teachers and
169 increase entropy during training.

170 In the industrial context, specific methods have emerged to address unique
171 domain challenges. TSKD [26] proposes a semantic-aware distillation at three
172 levels: capturing intra- and inter-class variation through graph modeling,
173 leveraging global semantics via attention maps and expert priors, and in-
174 cluding cross-level responses among features, relations, and logits. Zhao *et*
175 *al.* [48] build upon DeiT [24] to transfer spatial knowledge from CNNs to
176 ViTs using dense predictions, avoiding direct feature matching. Zhang *et*
177 *al.* [25] employ reverse distillation using one teacher and two students to
178 capture local and global structures for unsupervised anomaly detection. A
179 contextual affinity loss is defined to maintain spatial similarity, although
180 using multiple decoders may limit applicability in resource-constrained set-
181 tings. RD++ [29] introduces a multi-task reverse distillation scheme where

182 simulated perturbations, such as simplex noise, act as pseudo-anomalies, al-
183 though they risk introducing artifacts during training. Similarly, ROADS [14]
184 integrates prompt and vision into a reverse distillation framework to handle
185 distribution shifts. EfficientAD [49] performs anomaly detection at both the
186 logical and structural levels, prioritizing computational efficiency through
187 the use of a student–teacher framework and an autoencoder for global im-
188 age analysis. A lightweight student network is trained to replicate the fea-
189 tures extracted by a pre-trained teacher network using only normal samples.
190 Anomalies are then detected when the student network fails to accurately
191 reproduce these features. However, EfficientAD may encounter limitations
192 when the predictions of the student and teacher networks diverge, potentially
193 leading to an increase in false positives. Feng *et al.* [50] overcome the com-
194 putational demands of multi-step diffusion models by distilling a multi-step
195 teacher diffusion model into a single-step student generator.

196 2.2. Explainable Vision Transformers

197 Self-attention enables rich global context modeling, but this also intro-
198 duces challenges for interpretability. While straightforward techniques (*e.g.*,
199 Grad-CAM [20] or LayerCAM [51]) cannot be directly applied to Vision
200 Transformers (ViTs) due to their fundamentally different mechanisms for
201 producing visual explanations, several methods have been proposed to en-
202 hance the interpretability of ViTs, primarily via attention maps [52, 53] or
203 learned masking strategies [54]. Yu *et al.* [55] propose a Siamese framework
204 with normalization and decomposition modules to generate diverse and dis-
205 criminative class-specific attributes. TransCAM [56] combines convolutional
206 and transformer-based layers to improve class activation maps (CAMs), using
207 attention weights atop the Conformer architecture [57] to refine spatial local-
208 ization. Efficiency- and interpretability-focused variants such as LeViT [58]
209 and MiniViT [59] include convolutional-like pooling or layer-sharing tech-
210 niques. These designs require heavy modifications to the network, aiming to
211 balance interpretability, diversity, and training stability.

212 To improve features representations in the industrial domain, Zhang and
213 Liu [60] present a self-supervised framework for homogeneous attention-
214 based networks, using multi-view augmentations to improve feature trans-
215 fer. UniAS [16] bridges CNNs and Transformers by transforming convolu-
216 tional features into patch-based representations for coarse-to-fine segmenta-
217 tion, helping to model fine-grained variability. AnomalyDINO [61] applies
218 patch-based similarity using memory banks to spot anomalies; however, the

219 quality of the memory bank can impact detection reliability. DRAEM [62]
220 employs two networks, a reconstructive module to model normality and
221 a discriminative one to identify defects, though its reliance on synthetic
222 out-of-distribution samples may limit generalization. PromptAD [63] in-
223 tegrates CLIP [64] to extract language-informed visual features. Its multi-
224 branch architecture enables zero-shot detection by combining anomalous and
225 non-anomalous representations, though it still requires samples from related
226 anomaly classes for optimal performance.

227 *2.3. Generative Models*

228 Due to the scarcity of anomalous samples, generative models are of-
229 ten leveraged to compensate for the limitations of training data-driven ap-
230 proaches. While GAN-based methods [65, 66, 67] struggle to effectively cap-
231 ture both intra- and inter-class variability, recent efforts have shifted toward
232 diffusion-based techniques [68, 69]. For example, AnoDiff [5] employs a la-
233 tent diffusion model pre-trained on large-scale datasets to enable few-shot
234 anomaly synthesis. It introduces spatial anomaly embeddings to disentangle
235 appearance from location and includes adaptive attention reweighting
236 to enhance alignment with ground-truth masks. By contrast, AnoGen [10]
237 learns an explicit anomaly distribution, which is embedded and used to con-
238 dition a diffusion model alongside bounding box information. This design
239 facilitates weakly supervised learning by generating realistic anomalous sam-
240 ples. Compared to earlier works that often required separate models for
241 each anomaly type, SeaS [70] proposes a unified generative model. It is
242 able to produce diverse anomalies by leveraging a U-Net architecture with
243 separation-and-sharing fine-tuning. To address the challenge of generating
244 novel anomaly types, AnomalyAny [71] introduces a framework based on
245 Stable Diffusion [72], enabling the generation of anomalies conditioned on
246 a single normal sample and corresponding text descriptions. This approach
247 can synthesize high-quality, previously unseen anomalies without the need
248 for extensive training data. However, directly applying Stable Diffusion for
249 anomaly generation may result in unrealistic patterns if not properly guided.

250 **3. Method**

251 CNNs rely on local receptive fields, while ViTs use attention maps to iden-
252 tify the most important image regions for classification. This property makes
253 ViTs particularly suitable for anomaly detection, where both classification

Figure 1: Training and inference pipelines of the proposed framework. The teacher is trained for classification only, while the student performs all tasks and is trained via knowledge distillation. Neural network components (in blue), functional modules (in red), loss functions (in green), and the backpropagation operation (dotted) are depicted. Best viewed in color.

254 and detection/localization of defective regions are required. For this purpose,
 255 we propose a unified framework that extends the capabilities of ViTs beyond
 256 classification. It leverages attention maps to highlight structural anomalies
 257 while employing a convolutional network-based teacher model to guide
 258 the training process through knowledge distillation. Due to the scarcity of
 259 anomalous samples in industrial scenarios, we consider diffusion-based generative
 260 models for synthesizing input image/mask pairs. In the following,
 261 we detail our approach (depicted in Fig. 1), describing both the teacher and
 262 student networks, and the progressive masking mechanism used for guided
 263 training.

264 **Teacher Network.** Given an input image $\mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$, where (H, W)
 265 represents the image resolution and C the number of channels, we first train
 266 a CNN as a teacher model to classify the image as either normal or defective
 267 (more details about the different input settings are provided in Section 4).
 268 Let N_{def} denote the number of defect types within an object category T .
 269 To perform this classification task, we modify the final classification layer
 270 to predict $N_{def} + 1$ classes, discriminating between normal and defective
 271 instances. Given \mathbf{y} and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}^{teacher}$ as the ground-truth and predicted labels,
 272 respectively, the teacher network is trained using a standard cross-entropy
 273 loss function, $\mathcal{L}_{CE}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}^{teacher}, \mathbf{y})$.

274 Additional supervision may be provided in the form of fine-grained annotations,
 275 such as pixel-level masks, or coarse-grained labels, such as bounding
 276 boxes. To leverage this information, we adopt a late fusion strategy, where
 277 RGB images and annotations are processed through separate branches before
 278 being concatenated at the classification layer. Specifically, the primary
 279 network branch extracts high-level representations from the image, while a
 280 dedicated branch, named Mask-CNN, processes the mask annotations, capturing
 281 spatial defect information. Further details about the mask branch
 282 are provided in Section 4. The extracted features are then concatenated and
 283 passed through a classification layer, allowing the model to integrate complementary
 284 information while separately processing each piece of information.

285 **Student Network.** Instead of employing additional explainability techniques,
 286 we adopt a ViT-based student network to inherently leverage its self-attention
 287 maps for defect localization and detection tasks. In the following, we provide
 288 a brief overview of its main elements essential to our work. More specifically,
 289 a ViT processes an input image $\mathbf{I} \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W \times C}$ by dividing it into smaller
 290 patches $\mathbf{I}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times (P^2 \cdot C)}$, where (P, P) denotes the patch resolution.
 291 The number of resulting patches is given by $N = HW/P^2$. To

292 perform classification, an additional learnable embedding (z_{class}) is preprend
 293 to the embedded patches. These patches are then processed by a trans-
 294 former encoder, which applies normalization and multi-headed self-attention
 295 layers [73]. The input projections for the self-attention mechanism, namely
 296 key, query, and value, are computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{x}\mathbf{W}^K, \quad \mathbf{K} = \mathbf{x}\mathbf{W}^Q, \quad \mathbf{V} = \mathbf{x}\mathbf{W}^V, \quad (1)$$

297 where \mathbf{W}^K , \mathbf{W}^Q , and \mathbf{W}^V are projection matrices in $\mathbb{R}^{d_{model} \times d_k}$. Typically,
 298 $d_k = d_{model}/h$, where $d_{model} = 512$ and h represents the number of attention
 299 heads (e.g., $h = 8$). The attention function is computed as:

$$\text{Attention}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{K}, \mathbf{V}) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{K}^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{V}, \quad (2)$$

300 where $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$ is the attention weight matrix. The transformer consists of
 301 L stacked identical layers, each refining the previous representation. By ex-
 302 tracting the attention maps corresponding to the classification token, one can
 303 visualize the regions influencing the classification decision. Since CNNs have
 304 been shown to be more efficient in low-data regimes, we rely on DeiT [24],
 305 which introduces a knowledge distillation mechanism tailored for ViTs, which
 306 includes an additional distillation token that interacts with other tokens in
 307 the self-attention mechanism and is explicitly trained using labels from a
 308 CNN-based teacher model. While classification results can be obtained from
 309 the final multi-layer perceptron (MLP), the image regions responsible for the
 310 prediction mainly rely on the attention maps \mathbf{A} . To interpret the regions
 311 influencing classification, we consider attention rollout [52]. Given that ViTs
 312 consist of multiple attention layers, attention rollout aggregates attention
 313 maps across layers by recursively multiplying them. This cumulative ef-
 314 fect captures how much each input token contributes to the final prediction.
 315 More in details, for an input with $N + 2$ tokens (including the classifica-
 316 tion and distillation tokens) at the l^{th} layer, an attention map is defined as
 317 $\mathbf{A}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N+2) \times (N+2)}$. Attention rollout includes both direct attention and
 318 residual connections as $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(l)} = \alpha_{roll}\mathbf{A}^{(l)} + (1 - \alpha_{roll})\mathbf{I}_{N+2}$. Finally, the aggre-
 319 gated attention map is computed recursively as $\mathbf{A}_{roll} = \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(1)} \times \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(2)} \times \dots \times \tilde{\mathbf{A}}^{(L)}$,
 320 where N_a represents the total number of attention maps. The resulting ma-
 321 trix can be visualized as a heatmap, where each entry $\mathbf{A}_{roll}(i, j)$ represents
 322 the cumulative attention from token i to token j . In our work, we consider the
 323 image regions attended by the classification token, excluding the distillation
 324 patch, as it is only used in the knowledge transfer process.

325 **Student losses.** Our student network is trained using a combination
 326 of loss functions, addressing three distinct objectives: classification, local-
 327 ization/detection, and distillation. Specifically, both the classification and
 328 distillation objectives rely on the standard cross-entropy loss. We opt for a
 329 hard distillation approach, wherein the teacher’s classification outputs serve
 330 as hard labels for the student, as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}}^{\text{student}} = (1 - \alpha_{\text{KD}})\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}^{\text{student}}, \mathbf{y}) + \alpha_{\text{KD}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}}(\hat{\mathbf{y}}^{\text{student}}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}^{\text{teacher}}), \quad (3)$$

331 where $\hat{\mathbf{y}}^{\text{student}}$ represents the logits of the student networks associated with
 332 the classification head. Rather than employing a soft-distillation procedure,
 333 we choose hard-distillation for two main reasons: first, it has been shown
 334 to enable more effective knowledge transfer from a CNN-based teacher [24];
 335 second, due to the limited number of classes for our experiments, typically
 336 less than 10 per object, a soft-distillation strategy would introduce additional
 337 noise that is not beneficial for our task.

338 **Progressive Masked Focal Loss.** Including additional supervision in
 339 the form of masks \mathbf{M} can enhance the learning process by guiding attention
 340 maps toward the most relevant regions, such as defective areas. However,
 341 defective regions typically represent only a small fraction of an image, leading
 342 to a significant imbalance between defective and normal areas. To address
 343 this problem, we rely on the focal loss [74], following [5, 62], to improve
 344 the estimation of defective regions. This approach reduces the dominance of
 345 well-classified examples in the loss function, ensuring a greater focus on rare
 346 and difficult cases. The focal loss is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{FOC}}(p_t) = -\alpha_t(1 - p_t)^\gamma \log(p_t), \quad (4)$$

347 where p_t denotes the model’s estimated probability for the correct class, α_t
 348 is a balancing factor, and γ controls the attenuation of easy examples. To
 349 further enhance the robustness and generalization of attention maps, we in-
 350 troduce a progressive masked focal loss (PMFL) mechanism. While Yang *et*
 351 *al.* [43] propose a similar distillation procedure based on masking only specific
 352 layers via mimicking and generation procedures, our technique progressively
 353 applies a simpler adaptive masking across multiple attention layers while
 354 leveraging focal loss to improve optimization in imbalanced learning scenar-
 355 ios. In this way, we avoid explicitly defining shallow and deeper layers while
 356 providing a more robust generalization capability.

357 Our objective is to encourage attention maps, particularly in deeper lay-
 358 ers, to focus on defective regions with higher precision. More specifically,
 359 for the i^{th} attention map $\mathbf{A}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times P^2}$, where B is the batch size and P^2 is
 360 the total number of patches, we down-sample the target mask \mathbf{M} to reduce
 361 computational overhead. A binary mask $\mathbf{M}_i \in \{0, 1\}^{B \times P^2}$ is then sampled
 362 using a Bernoulli distribution with a head-dependent probability:

$$\mathbf{M}_i \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p_i), \quad p_i = p_{\min} + (p_{\max} - p_{\min}) \times \frac{i}{N_a}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_a, \quad (5)$$

363 where $p_{\min}, p_{\max} \in [0, 1]$ define the minimum and maximum retention proba-
 364 bilities, respectively, and N_a represents the total number of attention maps.
 365 For example, with $p_{\min} = 0.1$ and $p_{\max} = 1.0$, only 10% of attention values
 366 are retained in the earlier layers, whereas 100% of the attention values are
 367 preserved in the deeper layers.

368 The masked out elements are removed from both the attention map and
 369 the target mask as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i = \mathbf{A}_i \odot \mathbf{M}_i, \quad \hat{\mathbf{M}}_i = \mathbf{M} \odot \mathbf{M}_i, \quad (6)$$

370 where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication. The final loss is computed
 371 using the focal loss function (we omit for simplicity the input parameters):

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{PMFL}} = \frac{1}{N_a} \sum_i \mathcal{L}_{\text{FOC}}(\hat{\mathbf{A}}_i, \hat{\mathbf{M}}_i), \quad i = 1, \dots, N_a. \quad (7)$$

372 By progressively varying the masking ratio across layers, this approach en-
 373 sures that deeper layers emphasize annotated defects while maintaining sta-
 374 ble training. Finally, the overall loss function is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}^{\text{student}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{KD}}^{\text{student}} + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{PMFL}}^{\text{student}}. \quad (8)$$

375 This formulation enables the student ViT model to effectively learn both
 376 classification and localization/detection tasks by leveraging teacher-guided
 377 distillation alongside attention-driven defect localization.

378 4. Results

379 Our analysis focuses on assessing the performance of the proposed ap-
 380 proach across various input settings and comparing different architectures

Figure 2: Defective samples from the selected datasets: (a) and (b) transistor (damaged case) and hazelnut (crack), (c) bolt and ribbon, (d) fray and break, and (e) missing hole and short.

381 for both classification and detection/localization tasks. Below, we present
 382 a comprehensive overview of the datasets used, the evaluation protocols ap-
 383 plied, the experimental results obtained, and a series of ablation studies
 384 conducted to further examine the key components of our method.

385 **Datasets.** We consider four distinct datasets, collected under varying
 386 scenarios, to evaluate our framework and ensure its applicability across a
 387 range of real-world conditions. Firstly, we use the MVTec Anomaly De-
 388 tection (MVTec AD) [75] dataset, a standard benchmark for evaluating in-
 389 dustrial inspection methods. It consists of high-resolution images across 15
 390 object and texture categories, including both normal and defective samples.
 391 Each category includes various types of anomalies, such as scratches, defor-
 392 mations, and contaminations, along with pixel-wise ground truth masks to
 393 enable precise defect localization. For training our models, we rely on syn-
 394 thetic images generated by two diffusion-based models specifically designed
 395 to solve both classification and detection/localization tasks, *i.e.*, AnoDiff [5]
 396 and AnoGen¹ [10]. Since synthetic datasets are usually preprocessed through

¹As its cleaned version does not provide the *flip* defect for the metal nut category, we exclude this defective class from our experiments for this dataset.

397 a cleaning procedure, we use data from official repositories, including ~ 500
398 images/defect. As normal samples, we use the images provided by the MVTec
399 AD dataset (~ 200 images/category). A comparison of the training images is
400 shown in Figure 2a and Figure 2b. As test set, we consider the image/mask
401 pairs from the official split.

402 Then, we consider the RAD (Robust Anomaly Detection) [76] dataset,
403 which is specifically designed to evaluate the robustness of image anomaly
404 detection methods under realistic industrial conditions. Unlike the MVTec
405 AD dataset, which primarily focuses on detecting product defects, RAD em-
406 phasizes the identification of foreign objects on industrial work platforms.
407 The dataset introduces several sources of imaging noise, *e.g.*, varying view-
408 points (camera angles and object positions), uneven illumination (including
409 bright spots and shadows), and image blur (caused by defocus and motion),
410 which are often combined within the same image, making RAD a challenging
411 benchmark for anomaly detection. The dataset comprises 286 normal sam-
412 ples, of which 213 are used for training and 73 for testing. In addition, it
413 includes 1,224 abnormal samples across four categories: 327 for bolt, 293 for
414 ribbon, 281 for sponge, and 323 for tape. In our study, all normal samples
415 are combined to form a single good class, resulting in a total of five classes
416 (*i.e.*, 1 normal + 4 abnormal). For each anomalous class, we adopt an ap-
417 proximate 75%/25% split for training and testing, respectively. Figure 2c
418 shows two samples from this dataset.

419 Additionally, we test our framework against the Magnetic Tile Surface
420 Defect (MTSD) [77] dataset, which is designed to detect surface defects in
421 magnetic tiles under real-world industrial conditions. This dataset empha-
422 sizes low-contrast surface defects that occur in textured industrial materials,
423 presenting unique challenges due to the high intra-class variance, irregular
424 defect shapes, and complex illumination conditions. The dataset comprises
425 1,344 images, from which regions of interest (ROIs) are cropped to focus
426 on five specific defect types: blowhole, crack, fray, break and uneven. The
427 dataset also contains a defect-free (free) class. Pixel-level ground truth anno-
428 tations are provided for each ROI, enabling precise saliency-based evaluation.
429 In our study, we consider six classes (*i.e.*, 1 normal and 5 abnormal). For
430 each class, we adopt an approximate 75%/25% split for training and testing,
431 respectively. Figure 2d shows some images and masks from this dataset.

432 Finally, we consider the PCB defect [78] dataset, which contains high-
433 resolution images of printed circuit board (PCB) defects and is specifically
434 constructed for the task of tiny defect detection. It comprises 693 PCB

Table 1: Overview of input settings used in our experiments.

Input Setting	Acronym	Image		
		Defective	Good	Background
Standard	<i>STD</i>	✓	✗	✗
Standard + Good	<i>STD+G</i>	✓	✓	✗
Standard + Background	<i>STD+BG</i>	✓	✗	✓
Standard + Good + Background	<i>STD+G+BG</i>	✓	✓	✓
Binary	<i>B</i>	✓(Combined)	✓	✗
Binary + Background	<i>B+BG</i>	✓(Combined)	✓	✓

435 images with an average resolution of 2777×2138 pixels, each annotated with
 436 one or more instances of six common defect types: missing hole, mouse bite,
 437 open circuit, short, spur, and spurious copper. Due to the limited number of
 438 original samples and inherent class imbalance, extensive data augmentation
 439 was employed to enhance generalization and mitigate overfitting. As a result,
 440 the augmented dataset contains 10,668 images, partitioned into 8,534 training
 441 and validation samples, and 2,134 testing samples. This dataset presents
 442 significant challenges for defect detection due to the small size of the defects
 443 relative to the overall image dimensions and the presence of multiple defect
 444 types within single images. To address these challenges, we divide each
 445 600×600 augmented image into nine non-overlapping patches, each treated
 446 as an individual sample. To reduce training time, we further sub-sample
 447 both the training and testing sets by randomly retaining only one-tenth of
 448 the patches. Figure 2e shows two samples of cropped PCBs from this dataset.

449 **Classification Task.** As reported in Table 1, we consider six different
 450 configurations, *i.e.*, variations of the input setup, to assess the effectiveness
 451 of the classification architectures. More specifically, *STD* refers to a stan-
 452 dard configuration where only defective classes are considered. The number
 453 of defective classes for each category in the MVTec AD dataset is reported in
 454 Table 2. We modify this setup by also including normal samples (*STD+G*),
 455 allowing for a more comprehensive evaluation of the classifier’s ability to
 456 discriminate between multiple classes. Since low-cost sensors may partially
 457 capture the object along with the background, we investigate the potential
 458 impact of background elements on classifier performance by including back-
 459 ground images in the *STD+BG* and *STD+G+BG* configurations (a detailed
 460 description of the background class is provided below). Finally, we construct
 461 a binary scenario by grouping all defect types into a single class along with
 462 the normal samples (*B*), as well as an extended version that also includes

Table 2: Number of classes for each category in the MVTec AD dataset used in the *STD* input setting.

Objects	
Category	Num. Classes
Toothbrush	1
Bottle	3
Hazelnut, Metal Nut, Transistor	4
Capsule, Screw	5
Pill, Zipper	7
Cable	8
Textures	
Category	Num. Classes
Carpet, Grid, Leather, Tile, Wood	5

463 the background ($B+BG$). We report the standard top-1 accuracy, defined
 464 as the proportion of correctly classified test samples out of the total num-
 465 ber of test samples. This metric is applied to both multi-class and binary
 466 classification tasks. The number of classes used in our classification exper-
 467 iments varies by MVTecAD category under different input settings. Under
 468 the *STD* setting, each defect type is treated as a separate class. The *STD+G*
 469 and *STD+BG* settings each introduce one additional class by adding normal
 470 or background samples, respectively, while the *STD+G+BG* setting includes
 471 both. In contrast, the *B* and *B+BG* settings use 2 and 3 classes, respectively,
 472 by merging all defect types into a single defective class and optionally includ-
 473 ing background images. The toothbrush category of the MVTec AD dataset
 474 is excluded from the *STD* setting due to having only a single defect type,
 475 while texture categories are not evaluated in settings involving background
 476 images. To comprehensively evaluate model performance, each configuration
 477 is assessed using two distinct protocols:

- 478 • **Training-aware (TR-AW) Strategy:** Model performance is tracked
 479 on the training set using the loss function, without access to validation
 480 or test data.
- 481 • **Test-aware (T-AW) Strategy:** Model performance is evaluated di-
 482 rectly on the test set, without considering validation dynamics. While
 483 this may lead to overly optimistic results, it provides an estimate of the
 484 model’s upper-bound performance. This strategy is adopted in [5, 62].

485 **Background Class.** To generate background-only images, we process a
486 subset of randomly selected training (non-defective) images by applying bi-
487 nary masks that remove object regions while retaining peripheral areas. Since
488 anomalies in the MVTec AD dataset typically dominate the central portion
489 of the image, we preserve the left and right borders, which are more likely to
490 contain background content. We then apply an inpainting algorithm [79] to
491 fill the masked regions using surrounding pixels, thereby eliminating object-
492 specific information and producing visually coherent background textures.
493 This approach aims to preserve only background characteristics while mini-
494 mizing the presence of residual object features. Although the RAD, MTSD,
495 and PCB datasets do not explicitly contain objects, we decide to include
496 this fictitious class to represent anomalies in the capturing process, *e.g.*, fail-
497 ures in cameras used to collect the data. In these cases, we adopt the same
498 technique of MVTec AD dataset by only preserving left and right borders.
499 Representative examples of the resulting background images are shown in
500 Figure 3, featuring normal samples (top row) and background images (bot-
501 tom row) generated by our simple image processing pipeline for three cate-
502 gories, hazelnut, cable, and transistor, from the AnoDiff dataset, and normal
503 samples from the other datasets. Categories such as transistor and cable
504 exhibit more complex backgrounds, making it challenging to extract them
505 solely from image borders. For the MVTec AD dataset, the background class
506 is defined only for object categories, as discriminating between object and
507 background in texture categories is inherently ambiguous. Therefore, when
508 background images are included in the input setting, texture categories are
509 excluded from the evaluation, and results are reported only for the object
510 categories.

Figure 3: Normal and background samples generated for our datasets using our image processing pipeline.

511 **Detection and Localization Tasks.** Detection and localization tasks
512 consist in identifying defective regions at both image and pixel levels. For
513 detection and localization tasks, we employ metrics that better reflect spatial
514 and score-based prediction quality. Specifically, we evaluate anomaly detec-
515 tion performance using three standard metrics: Area Under the Receiver
516 Operating Characteristic Curve (AUC), Average Precision (AP), and Max-
517 imum F_1 -max ($F1_{\max}$). These metrics are computed at two levels of gran-
518 ularity, pixel-level and image-level. To assess spatial localization accuracy
519 (pixel-level), we evaluate predicted anomaly maps against binary ground-
520 truth masks. Both maps are flattened across the dataset to form pixel-wise
521 score-label pairs. Based on these, we compute each metric as follows:

$$\text{AUC} = \int_0^1 \text{TPR}(t) d\text{FPR}(t), \quad (9)$$

$$\text{AP} = \int_0^1 \text{Precision}(\text{Recall}) d(\text{Recall}), \quad (10)$$

$$F_1(t) = \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision}(t) \cdot \text{Recall}(t)}{\text{Precision}(t) + \text{Recall}(t)}, \quad (11)$$

$$F_1\text{-max} = \max_{t \in [0,1]} F_1(t). \quad (12)$$

522 In the above equations, TPR and FPR denote the true positive and false
523 positive rates. To evaluate anomaly detection at the image level, each image
524 is assigned a scalar anomaly score defined as the maximum value over its
525 predicted anomaly map. Given binary image-level labels $\mathbf{y} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicat-
526 ing normal ($\mathbf{y} = 0$) or anomalous ($\mathbf{y} = 1$) samples, we compute the same
527 set of metrics (AUC, AP, and F_1 -max) based on the predicted scores and
528 corresponding ground-truth labels.

529 Since detection and localization tasks are usually performed using both
530 defects and normal samples, we evaluate these tasks only using one input
531 setting, *i.e.*, $STD+G$. While the performance of ViT-based architectures is
532 evaluated using attention rollout [52], CNN-based architectures are assessed
533 using CAM-based methods. Specifically, we employ Grad-CAM [20], Grad-
534 CAM++ [80], LayerCAM [51], and Score-CAM [21], applied to the final
535 convolutional layer of each architecture.

536 **Baselines.** The teacher model is based on the RegNet-Y-16GF architec-
537 ture [81], pretrained on ImageNet-1k, and is used to extract features from

Table 3: Model specifications and performance of the architectures investigated in our study.

Model Complexity Comparison					
Category	Model	Params (M)	FLOPs (G)	Latency (ms)	Throughput (images/s)
Lightweight	SqueezeNet 1.0	0.74	1.48	10.94	91.60
	MobileNet V3	4.21	0.44	14.74	68.55
ResNet	ResNet-34	21.29	7.34	19.79	51.10
	ResNet-152	58.15	23.09	67.08	14.99
ViT	ViT-B-16 (S)	22.01	8.96	18.66	53.71
	ViT-B-16 (B)	57.45	23.51	50.80	19.75
	ViT-B-16 (L)	85.80	35.15	75.00	13.36
	CSKD-Ti	5.53	2.17	11.84	86.39
	CSKD-S	21.67	8.54	25.64	39.44
	CSKD-B	85.81	33.89	76.11	13.20
	OneN-S	22.02	8.65	18.74	53.43
	OneN-B	57.46	22.67	50.37	19.89
	OneN-L	85.81	33.89	76.05	13.17

538 RGB input images, while a DeiT-B [24] network is used as student. Our ap-
 539 proach is compared against models with similar computational complexity,
 540 including ResNet-34, ResNet-152, and ViT-B-16. For the ViT-B-16 archi-
 541 tecture, we consider three variants by limiting the number of transformer
 542 layers to 3 (S), 8 (B), and 12 (L). Additionally, we compare our models
 543 with CSKD [48], using its tiny (Ti), small (S), and base (B) variants. This
 544 approach is closely aligned with ours, as CSKD performs spatial-wise knowl-
 545 edge transfer from a CNN to a ViT. Similarly, we propose three variants
 546 of our architecture, *viz.*, small (OneN-S), base (OneN-B) and large (OneN-
 547 L), each containing 3, 8 and 12 transformer encoder layers, respectively.
 548 This design choice is intended to support a range of deployment scenarios
 549 with varying computational constraints. For example, OneN-L is tailored
 550 for high-accuracy applications, such as off-line inspections and detailed de-
 551 fect analyses, where computational resources are less restricted. In con-
 552 trast, OneN-S is optimized for real-time operations in resource-constrained
 553 environments, including live production line monitoring and embedded in-
 554 dustrial systems. Positioned between these extremes, OneN-B provides a
 555 balanced trade-off between accuracy and efficiency, making it suitable for
 556 semi-real-time inspection tasks or systems with moderate hardware capabil-
 557 ities. Table 3 presents the computational complexity of each architecture

558 in terms of the number of parameters, FLOPs (Floating-Point Operations),
 559 latency, and throughput, all measured on an Intel[®] Core[™] i7-7800X @ 3.50
 560 GHz CPU. Among the attention-based networks, CSKD-Ti is the smallest
 561 and most parameter-efficient model, while the B and L variants are the most
 562 resource-intensive. ResNet-34 is comparable to our OneN-S model, while
 563 ResNet-152 aligns more closely with our medium-sized OneN-B. We also
 564 include two parameter-efficient models, MobileNet V3 and SqueezeNet 1.0,
 565 which are commonly used in resource-constrained environments. All models
 566 are pre-trained on the ImageNet-1k dataset. Our proposed models remain
 567 comparable to their ViT-based counterparts, differing only by the inclusion
 568 of an additional distillation token while the parameter-efficient models offer
 569 the lowest complexity.

570 **Implementation Details.** We resize the input images to 224×224
 571 pixels, use the Adam optimizer [82] with hyperparameters $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 =$
 572 0.999 , a learning rate of 0.0004 , and a batch size of 128 . Weight decay
 573 is set to 0.05 , and early stopping is applied with a patience of 35 epochs.
 574 For data augmentation, we apply random cropping (ensuring that the defect
 575 area is always included when the image contains a defect), Gaussian blurring,
 576 horizontal flipping, and random rotation up to 20 degrees, each with a 50%
 577 probability. The focal loss is used with parameters $\alpha_t = 1$ and $\gamma = 2$ while
 578 we train the student network setting α_{KD} to 0.5 .

579 Following previous studies [62, 5, 25], we employ a one-model-per-category
 580 setting, training a separate model for each category. Thus, for each experi-
 581 ment, we train 15 models and report the mean values of the evaluated metrics.
 582 We omit standard deviation for brevity, as our primary focus is on overall
 583 trends and relative performance across methods. To improve detection and
 584 localization performance, we compute the final attention map using the at-
 585 tention rollout method [52], applying a maximum operation and discarding
 586 the lowest 75% of attention values. We also set α_{roll} to 0.5 . Furthermore, the
 587 Mask-CNN processes the input mask through a dedicated branch consisting
 588 of three convolutional layers with increasing channel sizes ($32 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 128$),
 589 each followed by Batch Normalization, ReLU activation, and MaxPooling
 590 for downsampling. An adaptive average pooling layer then generates a 128 -
 591 dimensional feature representation, which is concatenated with features ex-
 592 tracted from the RGB image and passed through a fully connected layer for
 593 final classification.

594 **Quantitative Results.** In the following, we first present our quanti-
 595 tative results by reporting the performance of two reference classifiers for

Table 4: Classification performance for two simple classifiers across different input settings used in our experiments using the MVTEC AD dataset.

Input Setting	Random Classifier (%)	Mean CV	Majority Classifier (%)
<i>STD</i>	20.67	0.09	23.75
<i>STD+G</i>	19.19	0.34	31.43
<i>STD+BG</i>	20.44	0.07	31.31
<i>STD+G+BG</i>	16.41	0.36	33.99
<i>B</i>	50.00	0.47	73.31
<i>B+BG</i>	33.33	0.46	72.86

596 baseline comparison. Then, for each dataset considered, we describe both
 597 the classification and detection/localization results.

598 Table 4 presents the performance of two baseline classifiers: a random
 599 classifier and a majority-class classifier on the MVTEC AD dataset. The
 600 random classifier assigns labels uniformly at random across all classes, while
 601 the majority-class classifier always predicts the most frequent class observed
 602 in the test set. To contextualize the impact of class imbalance, we also report
 603 the coefficient of variation (CV) of the class distribution, which quantifies
 604 the relative dispersion of class frequencies (with $CV = 0$ indicating perfectly
 605 balanced classes and higher values reflecting greater imbalance). We recall
 606 that $0 \leq CV \leq \sqrt{n} - 1$, where n is the number of classes. On average,
 607 the random classifier achieves a classification accuracy of approximately 20%
 608 across input settings involving more than three classes. The reported CV
 609 values indicate that the *STD* and *STD+BG* settings have relatively balanced
 610 class distributions, while the remaining settings show greater imbalance. In
 611 some cases, a single class dominates the test set, accounting for as much as
 612 30% to 70% of all instances.

613 Table 5 presents the classification accuracies for the AnoGen dataset under
 614 the TR-AW and T-AW evaluation protocols across various input settings.
 615 This dataset includes weakly annotated masks that enhance classification
 616 performance across most settings. Our OneN-L model achieves the best
 617 performance overall, consistently ranking first or second among the evalu-
 618 ated methods. We observe that for input settings with only 2 or 3 classes,
 619 OneN-S, the smallest model in our family, achieves the highest performance
 620 under the TR-AW evaluation protocol. In contrast, the CSKD models and
 621 MobileNetV3 architectures perform close to random, indicating limited learn-
 622 ing. ViT models also generally perform poorly under this protocol, suggest-

Table 5: Average classification performance on the AnoGen dataset under TR-AW and T-AW strategies. OneN results are reported with (\square) and without (\times) weak masks. Best and second-best scores per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

		Accuracy (%)					
Model	Mask	<i>STD</i>	<i>STD+G</i>	<i>STD+G+BG</i>	<i>STD+BG</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>B+BG</i>
MobileNet V3	\times	20.65/32.92	19.26/37.34	19.59/35.96	17.65/35.49	33.88/58.63	19.46/43.64
SqueezeNet 1.0	\times	34.88/49.13	42.26/53.09	32.97/46.97	37.71/51.19	40.72/75.34	40.56/78.27
ResNet-34	\times	39.47/53.23	37.38/51.51	39.12/48.39	40.98/ <u>55.68</u>	44.35/ <u>79.13</u>	41.16/78.45
ResNet-152	\times	37.92/53.86	27.81/50.97	33.75/47.39	27.69/53.99	38.02/73.48	28.41/73.82
ViT-B-16 (S)	\times	42.57/48.87	40.94/48.54	42.25/43.06	40.91/51.53	28.31/69.21	29.86/71.86
ViT-B-16 (B)	\times	47.46/51.30	43.49/51.07	41.75/44.70	<u>47.88</u> /50.26	28.59/74.59	32.11/68.91
ViT-B-16 (L)	\times	<u>48.98</u> /53.01	40.90/51.23	41.46/47.01	46.32/52.47	29.97/74.09	30.62/74.83
CSKD-Ti	\times	20.82/23.20	19.41/21.28	18.24/22.55	29.30/34.07	45.18/67.82	51.37/74.61
CSKD-S	\times	20.82/23.20	19.41/21.28	18.24/22.55	29.30/34.07	45.18/67.82	51.37/74.61
CSKD-B	\times	22.83/26.35	20.78/26.13	22.17/22.77	27.29/33.76	57.23/65.06	36.91/74.62
OneN-S	\times	32.50/37.31	28.38/34.55	30.31/29.03	27.82/46.41	63.01 /75.03	55.44 /74.94
OneN-B	\times	45.73/53.12	<u>47.11</u> /53.78	43.60/46.88	36.65/52.97	52.10/76.92	38.73/75.17
OneN-L	\times	47.87/56.49	45.95/ <u>55.12</u>	48.65 / <u>52.39</u>	38.38/ 55.79	51.27/77.97	33.44/76.14
OneN-S	\square	36.52/44.80	33.19/39.14	33.52/37.98	38.47/41.35	58.19/63.06	52.88/76.93
OneN-B	\square	45.76/ <u>57.27</u>	44.35/54.29	37.91/43.55	46.75/50.31	<u>62.66</u> /77.70	<u>53.54</u> / <u>78.49</u>
OneN-L	\square	49.32 / 58.04	51.31 / 61.03	<u>44.42</u> / 54.41	50.59 /52.50	56.94/ 83.24	44.08/ 80.96

623 ing they learn incorrect patterns. This highlights a potential sensitivity of
624 ViT architectures to the absence of strong supervision or contextual cues, or
625 possibly a reliance on large-scale datasets for effective training. Under the
626 *STD* input setting, both our OneN-L model and the ViT-B-16 (L) network
627 show comparable performance under the TR-AW protocol. OneN-S, when
628 equipped with masks, improves classification performance across nearly all in-
629 put settings. This demonstrates that even smaller models can achieve robust
630 performance when guided by localized mask supervision, underscoring the ef-
631 ficiency and scalability of the OneN model family. Finally, when evaluating
632 smaller baseline models such as MobileNet V3 and SqueezeNet, we observe
633 limited classification performance. These architectures yield lower accuracy
634 across all input settings, suggesting that their lightweight design, while ef-
635 ficient, may not be adequate for the complexity of the AnoGen dataset,
636 especially in challenging settings such as *STD+BG*. ResNet-based architec-
637 tures, although more capable than the lightweight models, still fall short of
638 the performance achieved by our proposed OneN models.

639 Table 6 presents a detailed comparison of detection and localization per-
640 formance across various models and XAI methods at the pixel level, on the
641 AnoGen dataset. The OneN-B and OneN-L models demonstrate superior
642 performance, consistently achieving the highest values across all metrics.

Table 6: Average pixel-level localization performance on the AnoGen dataset using the *STD+G* protocol. OneN results are reported with (\square) and without (\times) weak masks. Best and second-best results per column are bolded and underlined.

Model	XAI Method	Mask	Pixel-level		
			AUC	AP	F ₁ -max
ResNet-34	GradCAM	\times	56.72	3.81	7.67
ResNet-34	GradCAM++	\times	56.31	3.95	7.67
ResNet-34	ScoreCAM	\times	58.13	4.00	7.95
ResNet-34	LayerCAM	\times	56.30	3.89	7.63
ResNet-152	GradCAM	\times	50.67	4.57	8.42
ResNet-152	GradCAM++	\times	51.92	5.58	9.42
ResNet-152	ScoreCAM	\times	65.30	5.72	10.81
ResNet-152	LayerCAM	\times	51.76	4.66	8.59
ViT-B-16 (S)		\times	79.49	12.63	18.74
ViT-B-16 (B)	Rollout	\times	84.18	14.62	21.64
ViT-B-16 (L)		\times	82.74	12.54	19.16
CSKD-Ti		\times	56.06	3.32	7.06
CSKD-S	Rollout	\times	61.10	3.53	7.34
CSKD-B		\times	61.88	3.93	7.95
OneN-S		\times	64.04	6.31	11.36
OneN-B		\times	74.67	14.73	21.11
OneN-L		\times	82.84	13.81	20.75
OneN-S	Rollout	\square	85.83	17.48	23.24
OneN-B		\square	88.61	20.90	27.47
OneN-L		\square	<u>88.55</u>	<u>19.05</u>	<u>26.02</u>

643 ViT-B-16 models also show comparable performance, suggesting that larger
644 model capacity is not strictly necessary for effective localization. By con-
645 trast, the ResNet-based models (ResNet-34 and ResNet-152) produce simi-
646 lar results, with Score-CAM typically emerging as the best-performing XAI
647 technique. This highlights a general limitation among these methods in gen-
648 erating fine-grained localization maps. The ViT-based models and the OneN
649 family benefit significantly from the attention rollout technique, whereas
650 CSKD architectures perform poorly across different metrics. We also ob-
651 serve that many methods suffer from low F₁-max and AP, primarily due to
652 degraded precision and recall under class imbalance. Consistent with pre-
653 vious classification experiments, when weak annotations are provided, the
654 performance of our OneN models, particularly when using attention rollout,
655 improves substantially, especially in terms of AP and F₁-max. Finally, all
656 models show similar image-level detection performance, with AUC, AP, and
657 F₁-max averaging 43.69, 71.00, and 83.69, respectively, and varying by no
658 more than 2%.

659 Table 7 presents the classification results on the AnoDiff dataset. Our

Table 7: Average classification performance on the AnoDiff dataset under TR-AW and T-AW strategies. OneN results are reported with no mask (\times), weakly-annotated mask (\square) and fine-grained mask (\checkmark). Best and second-best scores per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

		Accuracy (%)					
Model	Mask	<i>STD</i>	<i>STD+G</i>	<i>STD+G+BG</i>	<i>STD+BG</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>B+BG</i>
MobileNet V3	\times	19.80/35.05	17.41/38.15	22.58/40.17	16.24/44.11	46.95/57.92	27.46/52.77
SqueezeNet 1.0	\times	43.65/54.70	36.63/45.54	36.10/47.68	48.00/55.10	32.02/67.92	30.12/68.17
ResNet-34	\times	50.03/ 69.30	<u>41.41</u> /57.33	<u>45.99</u> / <u>58.21</u>	52.25/ 69.80	40.24/73.00	43.26/ <u>76.26</u>
ResNet-152	\times	44.30/ <u>64.81</u>	40.28/ 60.08	40.55/ 64.18	41.48/ 73.60	32.76/ <u>77.85</u>	29.19/75.93
ViT-B-16 (S)	\times	40.76/49.84	34.03/42.66	29.87/38.31	41.77/50.30	28.51/66.14	28.56/72.17
ViT-B-16 (B)	\times	50.44/58.13	38.68/51.66	37.35/47.86	54.07/57.21	30.97/72.08	28.56/73.97
ViT-B-16 (L)	\times	<u>50.45</u> /58.15	38.45/50.28	34.63/46.14	<u>55.90</u> /59.31	28.07/65.52	28.66/69.60
CSKD-Ti	\times	20.23/23.92	22.73/25.71	20.21/23.61	27.83/30.56	<u>49.39</u> /71.82	45.56/67.39
CSKD-S	\times	20.52/24.33	20.37/24.26	20.75/25.83	28.86/31.71	47.53/67.79	59.00 /68.75
CSKD-B	\times	24.52/24.76	23.77/33.20	17.11/28.74	29.10/32.12	40.61/72.18	54.17 /72.74
OneN-S	\times	29.81/37.21	33.55/38.24	26.69/34.70	26.03/39.54	42.78/74.96	46.12/73.84
OneN-B	\times	43.37/51.17	40.79/48.27	32.08/43.75	34.94/50.43	44.64/76.34	42.43/75.32
OneN-L	\times	46.18/56.15	40.86/50.51	36.60/51.36	43.43/55.80	41.14/73.65	39.54/75.22
OneN-S	\square	31.70/37.81	31.34/36.20	19.47/34.99	35.43/39.64	43.58/73.25	31.56/72.80
OneN-B	\square	39.29/47.33	35.89/43.36	22.15/39.67	36.59/46.81	40.76/74.87	22.51/73.51
OneN-L	\square	43.83/56.31	41.38/52.18	39.14/47.01	44.09/53.48	39.54/71.53	30.81/73.77
OneN-S	\checkmark	30.36/38.05	30.06/33.92	23.34/35.40	32.60/41.39	45.75/75.37	45.88/74.74
OneN-B	\checkmark	43.10/53.92	38.80/49.95	33.36/48.64	40.14/58.72	44.62/73.49	42.82/ 77.44
OneN-L	\checkmark	50.97 /61.66	47.12 / <u>58.73</u>	50.86 /57.18	56.88 /63.92	49.55 / 78.84	38.12/74.96

660 proposed OneN-L model achieves the best performance across nearly all in-
 661 put configurations under the fair evaluation protocol, namely TR-AW. This
 662 demonstrates that self-attention mechanisms can effectively capture subtle
 663 anomalous patterns from synthetic data. OneN-L particularly outperforms
 664 all competitors by a large margin, even when good and/or background sam-
 665 ples are included in the classification task. In contrast, CSKD-based models
 666 consistently underperform across all settings, except in the $B+BG$ confi-
 667 guration. We attribute this exception primarily to class imbalance issues in
 668 the dataset (see Table 4). Interestingly, ResNet-based architectures per-
 669 form strongly under the T-AW evaluation strategy, even without leverag-
 670 ing additional masks, by achieving high classification accuracy or ranking
 671 as the second-best model across diverse input settings. This indicates that
 672 ResNet models possess strong generalization capabilities. However, their
 673 performance plateaus when trained using the TR-AW evaluation protocol,
 674 revealing a gap between the representational quality of synthetic samples and
 675 the complexity of the networks.

676 Table 8 reports both detection and localization performance at the pixel
 677 level across various models and XAI methods on the AnoDiff dataset. Our
 678 OneN model family achieves the best overall metrics. Specifically, OneN-
 679 L yields the highest AUC score when fine-grained annotations are used,
 680 while both OneN-B and OneN-L achieve the best AP and F_1 -max values
 681 under weakly annotated masks. These results demonstrate that, even with
 682 weak supervision, our models are capable of effectively localizing industrial
 683 defects. In contrast, fine-grained annotations may negatively affect perfor-
 684 mance, potentially due to the lack of generalization learned during training.
 685 The ResNet-based models follow a similar trend observed in the AnoGen
 686 dataset, with Score-CAM providing the best performance, while CSKD mod-
 687 els struggle due to limited supervision. At the image level, we observe simi-
 688 lar performance across all methods, indicating comparable capabilities when
 689 localization is not required. As in the previous dataset, all models show simi-
 690 lar image-level detection performance, with AUC, AP, and F_1 -max averaging
 691 48.79, 74.21, and 84.34, respectively, and varying by no more than 2%.

692 From a category-level perspective, we note that classification performance
 693 is not uniformly distributed across categories. Categories such as capsule,
 694 pill, and screw remain particularly challenging due to the presence of small
 695 or low-contrast defects, especially under multi-class settings such as STD
 696 and $STD+G$. For instance, the accuracy for these categories frequently re-

Table 8: Average pixel-level localization performance on the AnoDiff dataset using the *STD+G* protocol. OneN results are reported with no mask (\times), weakly-annotated mask (\square) and fine-grained mask (\checkmark). Best and second-best results per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

Model	XAI Method	Mask	Pixel-level		
			AUC	AP	F ₁ -max
ResNet-34	GradCAM	\times	57.74	5.42	9.98
ResNet-34	GradCAM++	\times	56.89	5.42	10.22
ResNet-34	LayerCAM	\times	57.18	5.48	10.33
ResNet-34	ScoreCAM	\times	59.62	6.07	10.92
ResNet-152	GradCAM	\times	57.00	6.45	11.49
ResNet-152	GradCAM++	\times	59.68	6.65	11.28
ResNet-152	LayerCAM	\times	59.77	6.47	11.45
ResNet-152	ScoreCAM	\times	64.30	7.06	12.41
ViT-B-16 (S)		\times	70.76	9.00	14.64
ViT-B-16 (B)	Rollout	\times	82.48	14.76	21.58
ViT-B-16 (L)		\times	78.61	12.11	18.93
CSKD-Ti		\times	54.62	4.08	7.61
CSKD-S	Rollout	\times	61.93	4.98	9.44
CSKD-B		\times	62.51	5.36	10.05
OneN-S		\times	59.22	6.98	12.21
OneN-B		\times	71.43	12.32	18.77
OneN-L		\times	75.84	13.11	20.07
OneN-S		\square	71.89	17.60	26.72
OneN-B	Rollout	\square	76.08	20.90	28.97
OneN-L		\square	75.38	<u>20.56</u>	<u>28.89</u>
OneN-S		\checkmark	82.13	14.50	20.11
OneN-B		\checkmark	<u>84.79</u>	14.45	21.74
OneN-L		\checkmark	85.04	15.04	22.07

Table 9: Classification performance on the RAD dataset under TR-AW and T-AW strategies. OneN results are reported with (\square) and without (\times) weak masks. Best and second-best scores per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

Model	Mask	Accuracy (%)					
		<i>STD</i>	<i>STD+G</i>	<i>STD+G+BG</i>	<i>STD+BG</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>B+BG</i>
MobileNet V3	\times	16.78/36.64	18.66/32.19	18.66/44.18	34.59/27.05	45.72/72.26	28.60/60.10
SqueezeNet 1.0	\times	19.86/20.83	12.50/50.34	36.30/11.64	23.97/20.89	48.80/41.95	59.76/69.01
ResNet-34	\times	12.33/23.29	20.21/27.40	11.82/15.24	15.75/15.41	45.03/58.05	15.07/10.79
ResNet-152	\times	23.63/24.32	17.47/25.68	25.51/27.40	30.14/29.45	58.56/37.33	34.59/25.34
ViT-B-16 (S)	\times	96.92/97.60	48.97/52.40	47.43/81.68	96.23/97.60	50.00/71.06	52.05/87.33
ViT-B-16 (B)	\times	99.32/ 100.0	51.88/61.64	49.14/70.72	99.32/99.32	52.74/72.26	50.00/81.51
ViT-B-16 (L)	\times	99.32/ 100.0	48.80/92.64	48.12/74.66	97.95/ 100.0	50.00/70.89	49.83/71.23
CSKD-Ti	\times	48.97/56.51	18.66/48.80	54.62/55.65	42.81/49.66	52.05/73.80	55.48/56.16
CSKD-S	\times	37.67/57.53	35.45/53.77	23.12/89.04	52.74/88.70	50.00/79.11	50.68/52.57
CSKD-B	\times	96.92/96.58	78.94 /90.58	56.51/65.07	97.26/94.18	50.00/76.71	55.48/56.16
OneN-S	\times	93.49/95.21	67.29/68.49	55.14/58.56	94.52/95.55	50.00/56.16	50.00/62.33
OneN-B	\times	98.63/ <u>99.66</u>	50.34/77.74	47.95/ 97.95	99.32/ 100.0	52.05/82.19	50.68/56.85
OneN-L	\times	98.97/ 100.0	49.66/87.50	48.46/ <u>97.26</u>	99.32/ 100.0	50.00/81.16	50.00/69.35
OneN-S	\square	94.18/95.21	59.08/72.26	73.63/87.16	97.95/98.29	50.00/60.27	50.00/63.01
OneN-B	\square	98.97/ 100.0	<u>74.14</u> / 99.14	77.91 /93.84	96.92/ <u>99.66</u>	<u>73.29</u> / <u>93.15</u>	80.82 /99.32
OneN-L	\square	100.0 / 100.0	63.87/ <u>96.23</u>	<u>67.98</u> /80.14	100.0 / 100.0	51.37/80.14	51.20/ 100.0
OneN-S	\checkmark	95.89/99.32	73.63/89.90	62.33/91.10	97.60/97.95	50.68/72.60	50.00/56.85
OneN-B	\checkmark	<u>99.66</u> / 100.0	73.80/83.73	66.78/94.35	<u>99.66</u> / <u>99.66</u>	78.08 /91.78	<u>77.40</u> / <u>95.21</u>
OneN-L	\checkmark	100.0 / 100.0	51.37/88.01	49.83/94.52	<u>99.66</u> / <u>99.66</u>	50.00/ 97.09	50.00/82.02

697 mains below 30%. This limitation is partially alleviated in the *B* and *B+BG*
698 configurations, where combining all defect types into a single class simpli-
699 fies the classification task. By contrast, categories characterized by visually
700 distinct or structurally regular features, such as hazelnut, tile, metal nut,
701 and transistor, consistently show high and stable accuracy across most in-
702 put settings. Furthermore, a direct comparison between the two datasets
703 highlights notable differences in performance trends. On average, AnoGen
704 achieves superior results in configurations that include background and bi-
705 nary groupings (*B*, *B+BG*), with several challenging categories (*e.g.*, grid,
706 carpet, and tile) showing marked improvements in accuracy. By contrast,
707 AnoDiff demonstrates more stable performance under the standard multi-
708 class settings (*STD*, *STD+G*), especially in object-centric categories such as
709 bottle, transistor, and metal nut.

710 Table 9 presents the classification accuracies on the RAD dataset. This
711 dataset introduces real-world imaging challenges, including viewpoint varia-
712 tion, lighting inconsistencies, and motion blur, which together make classifi-
713 cation particularly difficult. Despite these complexities, our OneN framework

Table 10: Average pixel-level localization performance on the RAD dataset using the *STD+G* protocol. OneN results are reported with (\square) and without (\times) weak masks. Best and second-best results per column are bolded and underlined.

Model	XAI Method	Mask	Pixel-level		
			AUC	AP	F ₁ -max
ResNet-34	GradCAM	\times	69.60	5.94	11.48
ResNet-34	GradCAM++	\times	82.76	12.28	20.77
ResNet-34	ScoreCAM	\times	82.38	12.25	20.36
ResNet-34	LayerCAM	\times	83.27	13.08	21.69
ResNet-152	GradCAM	\times	51.64	3.00	5.94
ResNet-152	GradCAM++	\times	76.51	6.88	12.98
ResNet-152	ScoreCAM	\times	78.17	7.00	13.20
ResNet-152	LayerCAM	\times	76.59	6.64	12.55
ViT-B-16 (S)		\times	65.98	6.28	12.84
ViT-B-16 (B)	Rollout	\times	77.12	9.24	16.04
ViT-B-16 (L)		\times	74.52	12.58	21.90
CSKD-Ti		\times	73.09	11.29	22.37
CSKD-S	Rollout	\times	69.79	11.09	20.44
CSKD-B		\times	87.15	16.42	25.60
OneN-S		\times	85.29	15.91	23.41
OneN-B		\times	81.35	9.99	19.05
OneN-L		\times	83.21	11.37	20.91
OneN-S		\square	72.30	24.02	<u>32.99</u>
OneN-B	Rollout	\square	69.33	22.45	30.86
OneN-L		\square	71.31	<u>22.87</u>	32.18
OneN-S		\checkmark	92.94	43.97	47.78
OneN-B		\checkmark	<u>87.24</u>	14.91	23.82
OneN-L		\checkmark	85.68	13.38	21.97

714 consistently achieves the highest overall performance, ranking first or second
715 across nearly all input configurations. When equipped with weak mask su-
716 pervision, the OneN models achieve the highest accuracy under several set-
717 tings, highlighting the effectiveness of localized guidance without requiring
718 a large number of parameters. We also observe that smaller variants of our
719 model, such as OneN-S, demonstrate strong robustness, highlighting the scal-
720 ability and efficiency of the OneN family. In contrast to their performance
721 on the AnoGen dataset, ViT models perform considerably better on RAD,
722 frequently outperforming CNN-based baselines. The CSKD family exhibits
723 more mixed results, with performance varying across configurations. While
724 CNN baselines show some improvement under the T-AW evaluation protocol,
725 their overall performance remains limited, further emphasizing the challenges
726 posed by the RAD dataset and the constraints of lightweight architectures
727 in such complex scenarios.

728 Table 10 reports the average pixel-level localization performance on the

Table 11: Classification performance on the MTSD dataset under TR-AW and T-AW strategies. OneN results are reported with no mask (\times), weakly-annotated mask (\square) and fine-grained mask (\checkmark). Best and second-best scores per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

		Accuracy (%)					
Model	Mask	<i>STD</i>	<i>STD+G</i>	<i>STD+G+BG</i>	<i>STD+BG</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>B+BG</i>
MobileNet V3	\times	25.00/21.88	34.43/8.68	12.57/22.16	19.79/30.21	71.26/68.26	29.04/12.87
SqueezeNet 1.0	\times	25.00/11.46	17.07/29.04	17.66/45.51	25.00/27.08	71.26/52.10	27.54/69.46
ResNet-34	\times	18.75/32.29	57.49/21.26	12.28/45.51	26.04/30.21	32.63/65.57	14.07/21.56
ResNet-152	\times	25.00/36.46	28.74/22.46	13.77/18.56	20.83/34.38	44.91/64.07	46.11/68.26
ViT-B-16 (S)	\times	82.29/89.58	71.26/71.56	71.26/77.84	90.62/90.62	71.26/72.46	71.26/71.56
ViT-B-16 (B)	\times	95.83/ <u>97.92</u>	78.44/ <u>89.52</u>	79.34/ 86.83	<u>97.92/97.92</u>	88.32/89.52	79.04/83.83
ViT-B-16 (L)	\times	<u>94.79/98.96</u>	89.22/89.22	<u>81.74/84.73</u>	94.79/ 98.96	88.32/87.72	<u>82.04/84.73</u>
CSKD-Ti	\times	26.04/27.08	71.26/71.26	71.26/71.26	27.08/29.17	71.26/71.26	71.26/71.26
CSKD-S	\times	28.12/28.12	71.26/71.26	71.26/71.26	19.79/25.00	28.74/71.26	71.26/71.26
CSKD-B	\times	30.21/29.17	71.26/71.26	71.26/71.26	26.04/26.04	71.26/71.26	71.26/71.26
OneN-S	\times	53.12/53.12	71.26/71.26	70.36/71.26	50.00/54.17	71.26/71.26	70.96/71.26
OneN-B	\times	91.67/96.88	71.26/76.65	77.54/80.24	93.75/98.96	71.26/81.14	78.14/83.83
OneN-L	\times	97.92/98.96	82.34/87.72	86.23/86.83	95.83/ 98.96	83.23/87.72	83.53/88.02
OneN-S	\square	30.21/33.33	71.26/71.26	70.66/71.26	30.21/34.38	71.26/71.26	70.96/72.46
OneN-B	\square	39.58/42.71	71.26/71.26	71.26/75.15	79.17/76.04	71.26/71.56	70.96/71.86
OneN-L	\square	86.46/ 98.96	<u>82.93/87.43</u>	80.84/83.23	98.96/98.96	85.63/85.93	81.74/85.33
OneN-S	\checkmark	25.00/36.46	71.26/71.26	70.36/71.26	34.38/35.42	71.26/71.26	70.66/71.56
OneN-B	\checkmark	77.08/94.79	70.96/73.05	74.85/77.84	90.62/95.83	71.26/79.64	76.65/84.13
OneN-L	\checkmark	87.50/ 98.96	82.04/ 89.82	78.74/83.53	96.88/ 98.96	<u>85.93/88.02</u>	81.44/ <u>86.23</u>

729 RAD dataset. Our OneN framework demonstrates strong localization perfor-
730 mance, especially when guided by class-specific mask supervision. OneN-S
731 achieves the best performance across all three metrics when trained with
732 full mask guidance, outperforming all other models. Among the mask-
733 augmented configurations, OneN variants consistently surpass their corre-
734 sponding non-masked counterparts, demonstrating the critical role of even
735 weak spatial supervision in improving localization quality. OneN-S with par-
736 tial mask supervision attains the second-best F_1 -max, while OneN-L achieves
737 the second-best AP, further demonstrating the effectiveness of targeted guid-
738 ance for anomaly localization. Among the baseline models, CSKD-B shows
739 the strongest localization performance in the absence of mask supervision. Fi-
740 nally, all models show similar image-level detection performance, with AUC,
741 AP, and F_1 -max averaging 34.92, 41.21, and 66.67, respectively, and varying
742 by no more than 1%.

743 Table 11 reports the classification accuracies on the MTSD dataset. De-
744 spite the inherent challenges of this dataset, the proposed OneN-L model
745 consistently achieves superior performance, ranking first or second across

746 the majority of configurations and evaluation protocols. Notably, even in
 747 the absence of mask supervision, OneN-L outperforms all competing models,
 748 highlighting its robustness and strong generalization capabilities. The OneN-
 749 B variant also demonstrates competitive performance, particularly under the
 750 $B+BG$ and $STD+BG$ settings. The lightweight OneN-S model offers an
 751 effective balance between accuracy and computational efficiency, maintain-
 752 ing stable performance across various configurations. Transformer-based ViT
 753 models also exhibit strong results, particularly when compared to the smaller
 754 OneN variants, occasionally surpassing them in specific settings. In contrast,
 755 the CSKD models tend to exhibit consistent yet less adaptable performance
 756 across different strategies. Conventional CNN baselines, such as MobileNet
 757 V3 and SqueezeNet, generally underperform relative to both transformer-
 758 based and OneN models, underscoring the advantages of the OneN architec-
 759 ture in addressing the complexities of the MTSD dataset. Finally, all models
 760 show similar image-level detection performance, with AUC, AP, and F_1 -max
 761 averaging 48.97, 26.90, and 45.11, respectively, and varying by no more than
 762 2%.

763 Table 12 reports the pixel-level localization performance on the MTSD
 764 dataset using the $STD+G$ protocol. The OneN models achieve superior
 765 localization performance compared to all baselines. For example, OneN-L,
 766 when trained with weak mask supervision, obtains the best scores for the AP
 767 and F_1 -max metrics. OneN-B with weak supervision also performs strongly,
 768 ranking second in AP and F_1 -max. Interestingly, the performance of OneN-B
 769 and OneN-L drops only slightly when trained without masks, indicating that
 770 the OneN framework is inherently capable of capturing localized anomalies
 771 even in the absence of explicit spatial guidance. Among transformer base-
 772 lines, ViT-B-16 (L) achieves the best results. In contrast, CAM-based visual
 773 explanation methods applied to ResNet variants consistently yield poor lo-
 774 calization performance, with low AUC values. Nevertheless, absolute AP and
 775 F_1 -max values remain relatively low. This highlights the intrinsic difficulty
 776 of the MTSD dataset, which involves localizing fine-grained, low-contrast
 777 surface defects under variable illumination and complex backgrounds. In
 778 such scenarios, saliency-based methods often struggle to produce precise and
 779 dense activations, especially in the absence of a supervision.

780 Table 13 presents the average classification performance on the PCB
 781 dataset. Overall, OneN-L achieves the best results, obtaining the highest
 782 average accuracies across most evaluation protocols. This demonstrates its
 783 strong capacity to leverage weak supervision for improved classification. Even

Table 12: Average pixel-level localization performance on the MTSD dataset using the *STD+G* protocol. OneN results are reported with no mask (\times), weakly-annotated mask (\square) and fine-grained mask (\checkmark). Best and second-best results per column are bolded and underlined.

Model	XAI Method	Mask	Pixel-level		
			AUC	AP	F ₁ -max
ResNet-34	GradCAM	\times	52.87	2.60	5.00
ResNet-34	GradCAM++	\times	56.73	2.99	5.34
ResNet-34	ScoreCAM	\times	57.74	3.12	6.05
ResNet-34	LayerCAM	\times	56.92	2.98	5.41
ResNet-152	GradCAM	\times	47.44	2.35	4.37
ResNet-152	GradCAM++	\times	49.53	2.47	4.58
ResNet-152	ScoreCAM	\times	49.99	2.52	4.83
ResNet-152	LayerCAM	\times	49.98	2.53	4.88
ViT-B-16 (S)		\times	53.41	2.45	4.69
ViT-B-16 (B)	Rollout	\times	55.16	2.87	5.43
ViT-B-16 (L)		\times	56.95	2.91	5.82
CSKD-Ti		\times	52.37	2.73	5.33
CSKD-S	Rollout	\times	53.28	2.80	5.52
CSKD-B		\times	50.57	2.55	5.04
OneN-S		\times	53.04	2.41	4.76
OneN-B		\times	65.26	3.85	7.62
OneN-L		\times	57.85	2.84	5.51
OneN-S		\square	47.23	5.16	9.16
OneN-B	Rollout	\square	51.06	<u>5.56</u>	<u>10.16</u>
OneN-L		\square	56.58	6.39	11.88
OneN-S		\checkmark	48.12	2.32	4.48
OneN-B		\checkmark	59.91	2.94	5.71
OneN-L		\checkmark	<u>62.54</u>	3.13	6.49

784 without mask supervision, OneN-L maintains robust performance, frequently
785 ranking as the second-best model. OneN-B also performs competitively, par-
786 ticularly in the binary classification setting. Despite its compact architecture,
787 OneN-S delivers solid performance, often outperforming the CSKD variants,
788 thus providing an efficient yet effective solution.

789 Among transformer-based baselines, ViT models exhibit strong performance,
790 with larger variants such as ViT-B (L) and ViT-B (S) occasionally surpassing
791 smaller OneN models in specific configurations. This highlights the represen-
792 tational power of transformer architectures in modeling complex defect pat-
793 terns. In contrast, CSKD models yield lower but stable performance across
794 training settings, suggesting limited adaptability to the unique challenges
795 of the PCB dataset. Conventional CNN baselines underperform relative to
796 both the OneN models and the transformer-based baselines.

797 Table 14 reports pixel-level localization performance on the PCB dataset

Table 13: Average classification performance on the PCB dataset under TR-AW and T-AW strategies. OneN results are reported with no mask (\times) and weakly-annotated mask (\square). Best and second-best scores per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

		Accuracy (%)					
Model	Mask	<i>STD</i>	<i>STD+G</i>	<i>STD+G+BG</i>	<i>STD+BG</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>B+BG</i>
MobileNet V3	\times	19.94/21.05	16.15/16.63	8.79/17.34	15.24/15.51	52.08/52.91	33.24/44.46
SqueezeNet 1.0	\times	17.17/13.02	11.16/14.73	6.18/14.73	20.50/12.19	53.32/49.31	43.91/41.41
ResNet-34	\times	20.50/15.51	16.39/16.63	12.11/14.49	14.96/14.96	50.00/51.66	24.52/43.63
ResNet-152	\times	16.34/20.50	13.78/13.78	8.08/13.30	12.47/13.85	51.25/50.42	24.38/35.87
ViT-B-16 (S)	\times	19.67/23.82	18.29/17.81	22.80/23.28	16.34/25.48	63.43/65.10	61.36/ <u>68.01</u>
ViT-B-16 (B)	\times	18.28/27.15	16.63/20.19	18.76/21.62	21.05/26.59	64.68/65.24	50.00/66.62
ViT-B-16 (L)	\times	19.11/26.04	19.71/20.90	22.80/27.55	17.17/24.65	62.47/68.01	<u>68.14</u> /64.27
CSKD-Ti	\times	22.71/22.16	10.69/17.34	14.25/14.49	22.16/21.33	49.72/57.62	62.60/61.50
CSKD-S	\times	22.16/12.74	14.73/19.00	14.01/14.25	22.16/22.44	50.28/50.14	49.58/55.40
CSKD-B	\times	12.47/22.16	14.25/18.76	13.78/16.39	22.16/13.85	55.26/60.39	60.39/62.19
OneN-S	\times	22.16/24.93	13.30/14.25	13.78/19.71	14.96/21.88	62.60/ <u>67.17</u>	61.91/65.24
OneN-B	\times	19.94/22.44	15.44/16.86	16.86/21.38	22.44/24.93	61.36/65.51	59.28/66.07
OneN-L	\times	<u>29.92</u> / <u>36.57</u>	<u>27.55</u> / <u>28.74</u>	35.63 / <u>30.64</u>	<u>37.12</u> / <u>36.29</u>	53.46/66.07	64.82/67.73
OneN-S	\square	16.90/23.27	17.81/14.73	14.96/22.09	21.05/24.93	63.43/64.82	61.63/64.13
OneN-B	\square	16.34/24.93	17.81/16.86	16.15/22.57	18.56/26.59	<u>66.76</u> /64.68	63.30/67.04
OneN-L	\square	49.31 / 50.97	29.69 / 32.07	<u>34.68</u> / 40.14	46.26 / 52.08	66.90 / 68.56	69.39 / 68.56

798 using the *STD+G* protocol. The proposed OneN models outperform all
799 baselines in this setting. Specifically, when trained with weak mask supervi-
800 sion, OneN-L achieves the highest scores across all metrics, including AUC,
801 AP, and F_1 -max. Similarly, OneN-S and OneN-B under weak supervision
802 also rank among the top-performing methods, with OneN-S obtaining the
803 second-highest F_1 -max. Even without mask supervision, OneN models still
804 localize effectively fine-grained defects without explicit pixel-level guidance.
805 Among transformer-based models, ViT-B-16 (L) performs best, although it
806 still lags behind OneN-L. In contrast, conventional CNN models employing
807 CAM-based methods on ResNet backbones exhibit comparatively lower lo-
808 calization accuracy. These methods show limited sensitivity to subtle defect
809 cues, likely due to the coarse activation maps. Nonetheless, despite these re-
810 lative improvements, the absolute AP and F_1 -max values remain low across
811 all models. This highlights the intrinsic difficulty of the PCB dataset, where
812 defects tend to be small and localized, making precise spatial localization
813 challenging even for advanced architectures. Finally, all models show similar
814 image-level detection performance, with AUC, AP, and F_1 -max averaging
815 44.91, 84.05, and 92.33, respectively, and varying by no more than 1%.

816 **Qualitative Results.** Figure 4 presents a qualitative comparison of lo-
817 calization performance across the proposed OneN networks trained on the

Table 14: Average pixel-level localization performance on the PCB dataset using the *STD+G* protocol. OneN results are reported with no mask (\times) and weakly-annotated mask (\square). Best and second-best results per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

Model	XAI Method	Mask	Pixel-level		
			AUC	AP	F ₁ -max
ResNet-34	GradCAM	\times	56.94	2.26	4.44
ResNet-34	GradCAM++	\times	56.43	2.28	4.51
ResNet-34	ScoreCAM	\times	55.17	2.11	4.35
ResNet-34	LayerCAM	\times	56.39	2.23	4.44
ResNet-152	GradCAM	\times	52.38	1.95	3.96
ResNet-152	GradCAM++	\times	56.39	2.20	4.31
ResNet-152	ScoreCAM	\times	56.87	2.25	4.42
ResNet-152	LayerCAM	\times	56.57	2.21	4.33
ViT-B-16 (S)		\times	52.36	2.00	3.90
ViT-B-16 (B)	Rollout	\times	46.36	1.62	3.70
ViT-B-16 (L)		\times	55.34	2.19	4.34
CSKD-Ti		\times	51.92	1.99	3.78
CSKD-S	Rollout	\times	51.03	1.90	3.81
CSKD-B		\times	53.61	2.01	3.95
OneN-S		\times	44.75	1.55	3.69
OneN-B		\times	48.27	1.82	3.67
OneN-L		\times	46.53	1.63	3.67
OneN-S		\square	<u>58.47</u>	2.61	<u>5.36</u>
OneN-B	Rollout	\square	54.82	2.40	4.98
OneN-L		\square	63.82	2.85	5.73

Figure 4: Qualitative localization results of OneN models on the AnoDiff dataset with three supervision settings: no masks (1st row), weak masks (2nd row), and ground-truth masks (3rd row). Best viewed in color.

Figure 5: Qualitative localization results of OneN models on the RAD and MTSD datasets with three supervision settings: no masks (1st row), weak masks (2nd row), and ground-truth masks (3rd row). Best viewed in color.

818 AnoDiff dataset under different supervision levels. OneN-S is able to iden-
819 tify the anomaly regions but tends to slightly under-localize and produces
820 less focused activation maps, particularly when no additional masks or only
821 weakly annotated masks are used. OneN-B yields more accurate localization,
822 better aligning with the shape and position of the ground-truth masks. In
823 contrast, OneN-L delivers the most precise and confident localization, sug-
824 gesting that it benefits the most from its increased capacity, achieving strong
825 results even in the absence of fine-grained supervision. Our models are also
826 capable of localizing multiple defects, such as compound anomalies in the
827 wood or cable categories, by activating multiple regions corresponding to the
828 defective areas. These results highlight that weak annotations are beneficial
829 in most cases, enabling effective localization while significantly reducing the
830 cost and effort associated with labor-intensive annotation processes.

831 Figure 5 also illustrates localization performance of our OneN variants
832 on samples from the RAD and MTSD datasets. In the RAD dataset, for
833 both ribbon and bolt defect types, OneN-S generally succeeds in detecting
834 anomalous regions but often show fragmented or overly diffuse activation
835 maps. OneN-B shows better performance, especially for subtle defects, by
836 producing more structured and contiguous localization aligned with defect
837 morphology. While OneN-S presents better localization capability for the
838 ribbon class, OneN-L and OneN-B provide more accurate localization for the
839 bolt class. Similar trends are observed in the MTSD dataset, where OneN-
840 B delivers the most confident and spatially coherent localization, accurately
841 delineating uneven texture regions.

842 Figure 6 presents qualitative localization results of the proposed OneN
843 models on the PCB dataset, focusing on two representative defect types. In
844 the missing hole example, all models successfully activate around the defect
845 location, but the spatial extent and sharpness of the activations vary. OneN-
846 S produces relatively broad activation maps with weaker central focus, while
847 OneN-B shows more concentrated responses, though it occasionally over-
848 activates nearby non-defective regions. OneN-L produces the most precise
849 and sharply defined heatmaps, closely aligned with the actual defect loca-
850 tion, even in the absence of masks. When trained with weak supervision,
851 both OneN-B and OneN-L demonstrate improved localization. In the more
852 complex short defect case, localization becomes more challenging. Without
853 supervision, the OneN models tend to activate across multiple surround-
854 ing regions, often missing the precise defect boundaries. In contrast, guided
855 training improves localization accuracy, resulting in activations that are more

Figure 6: Qualitative localization results of OneN models on the PCB dataset with two supervision settings: no masks (1st row) and weak masks (2nd row). Best viewed in color.

Figure 7: Qualitative localization comparison on AnoGen (1st, 2nd rows) and AnoDiff (3rd, 4th) using our OneN-L model , alongside CNN and ViT-based models. GradCAM++ and attention rollout are used for generating heatmaps from CNNs and attention-based models, respectively. Best viewed in color.

856 tightly confined to the true defect regions, suggesting enhanced feature dis-
 857 crimination capabilities.

858 Figure 7 provides a visual comparison of localization performance among
 859 ResNet-based models, ViT-B-16 (L), CSKD-B, and our OneN-L network.
 860 The results show that OneN-B consistently produces sharper and more fo-
 861 cused localization maps, aligning more accurately with the ground-truth
 862 masks across both datasets. While ResNet-34 and ResNet-152 are able to
 863 highlight some anomalous regions, their responses tend to be less precise and
 864 occasionally fragmented. For instance, ResNet-34 struggles to identify com-
 865 plex anomaly patterns, often activating fixed, sharply defined regions that
 866 do not correspond to actual defects. In contrast, OneN-L benefits from its
 867 tailored architecture and mask-based supervision, resulting in more reliable
 868 and interpretable localization. CSKD-B appears unable to effectively detect
 869 defective regions in complex objects. For example, this network mistakenly
 870 identifies the black border of a zipper object as anomalous, and produces

Table 15: Comparison of various PMFL loss configurations evaluated on the wood category of the AnoDiff dataset using OneN-L trained with fine-grained annotations. Best and second-best results per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

Loss Params.			Pixel-level	
β	Progressive	Acc. (%)	AUC	AP
1	\times	75.95	31.67	66.09
1	\checkmark	72.15	25.35	62.87
3	\times	70.89	41.05	<u>68.64</u>
3	\checkmark	74.68	32.63	66.35
7	\times	75.95	35.13	67.72
7	\checkmark	78.48	<u>40.18</u>	71.38
10	\times	<u>77.22</u>	31.23	65.55
10	\checkmark	74.68	22.81	62.70

871 scattered or inconsistent results for other categories.

872 **Ablation studies.** In the following, we report both quantitative and
 873 qualitative ablation studies to evaluate the robustness of our family models.
 874 More specifically, Table 15 provides a comparison of different configurations
 875 of the proposed PMFL loss, examining the influence of the weighting parameter
 876 β and the presence of the progressive mechanism. Our experiments reveal
 877 that the configuration with $\beta = 7$ and the progressive mechanism yields the
 878 best overall performance, mainly in terms of accuracy and AP pixel-level,
 879 while also ranking second-best in pixel-level AUC.

880 Table 16 presents the classification results for both datasets, evaluated
 881 across several categories independently. Our OneN-L model typically achieves
 882 the best performance under both evaluation protocols. Interestingly, we ob-
 883 serve that additional input annotations are particularly useful for object-
 884 based categories, *e.g.*, hazelnut, whereas texture-based categories often per-
 885 form comparably well even without additional supervision. This suggests
 886 that weakly or finely annotated inputs provide more discriminative power
 887 in structured, patterned images. In several cases, the OneN-B model ben-
 888 efits from fine-grained annotations, achieving either the best or second-best
 889 performance. The OneN-S model exhibits stable performance under the TR-
 890 AW strategy regardless of annotation type, but shows greater sensitivity to
 891 annotations under the T-AW protocol. These results confirm the robustness
 892 of our model family across different supervision levels and input types.

893 Figure 8 shows a qualitative comparison corresponding to the experi-
 894 ments reported in Table 16 using both datasets. We observe that the OneN-B
 895 and OneN-L models produce correct classification predictions, with attention

Table 16: Classification results (%) on AnoGen ((a), (b)) and AnoDiff ((c), (d)) datasets for various categories under the *STD + G* input, evaluated with both TR-AW and T-AW strategy. Best and second-best per column are bolded and underlined, respectively.

Model	Mask	
	✗	□
OneN-S	45.30/50.43	48.72/51.28
OneN-B	<u>86.32</u> / 91.45	<u>77.78</u> / 88.89
OneN-L	88.03 / <u>90.60</u>	87.18 / <u>94.02</u>

(a) Tile

Model	Mask	
	✗	□
OneN-S	46.84/ <u>58.23</u>	60.76/68.35
OneN-B	<u>67.09</u> / 78.48	79.75 / 78.48
OneN-L	69.62 / 78.48	<u>74.68</u> / <u>75.95</u>

(b) Hazelnut

Model	Mask		
	✗	□	✓
OneN-S	<u>53.64</u> /50.91	52.73/52.73	49.09/62.73
OneN-B	44.55/ 74.55	<u>73.64</u> / <u>72.73</u>	<u>51.82</u> / 84.55
OneN-L	60.00 / <u>67.27</u>	77.27 / 81.82	63.64 / <u>80.91</u>

(c) Wood

Model	Mask		
	✗	□	✓
OneN-S	27.35/26.50	22.22/25.64	25.64/30.77
OneN-B	<u>42.74</u> / <u>44.44</u>	35.90 / <u>50.43</u>	<u>47.01</u> / 52.14
OneN-L	58.97 / 48.72	<u>31.62</u> / 58.97	50.43 / <u>52.14</u>

(d) Carpet

896 maps accurately focusing on the defective image regions. Although OneN-
 897 S makes an incorrect prediction for a sample image (see Figure 8a), it still
 898 successfully highlights most of the defective regions. In Figure 8b, OneN-S
 899 provides a correct prediction but yields more scattered activation maps, fail-
 900 ing to clearly identify the defective areas. In both Figure 8c and Figure 8d, all
 901 OneN variants correctly identify the defects, even when they are distributed
 902 across multiple regions of the image.

903 Figure 9 shows some representative failure cases of the OneN-L model’s
 904 defect localization performance across diverse industrial datasets. Each ex-
 905 ample highlights specific challenges encountered during anomaly detection,
 906 such as difficulty in precisely delineating subtle, linear defects within pat-
 907 terned backgrounds (see Figure 9a), or over-segmentation leading to broader
 908 detection on simpler objects (see Figure 9b). The model also shows diffi-
 909 culty with irregular, distributed defects (see Figure 9c), where localization is
 910 diffuse, and with accurately capturing slender, elongated anomalies (see Fig-
 911 ure 9d). Furthermore, we notice a recurring issue of over-extending the local-
 912 ization area beyond the actual defect boundary (see Figure 9e) and struggling
 913 to isolate small, distinct defects within complex, densely packed structures
 914 (see Figure 9f).

Figure 8: Classification and localization results of OneN models on the weakly supervised AnoGen dataset ((a), (b)) and the fully supervised AnoDiff dataset ((c), (d)). Classification outputs are color-coded (red: incorrect, green: correct). Best viewed in color.

915 **5. Conclusion**

916 Anomaly detection represents a fundamental task across various indus-
 917 trial domains, yet it remains challenged by factors such as human error,
 918 processing bottlenecks, limited adaptability of conventional deep learning
 919 approaches, and the scarcity of defective samples necessary for training ro-
 920 bust models. In this work, we propose a unified architecture capable of
 921 performing both classification and detection/localization, tasks that are con-
 922 ventionally addressed by separate models. Our method employs knowledge
 923 distillation to transfer representational knowledge from a high-capacity con-
 924 volutional neural network to attention-based models trained under different
 925 supervision regimes. To enhance localization accuracy, we introduce a pro-
 926 gressive masking mechanism that effectively guides attention maps toward
 927 precise defect regions. Comprehensive experimental evaluations demonstrate
 928 that the proposed approach achieves strong performance across diverse in-
 929 dustrial scenarios and input configurations, even under weak supervision.

Figure 9: Failure cases in localization maps from our OneN-L model trained on the considered datasets: (a) and (b) AnoDiff, (c) AnoGen, (d) RAD, (e) MTSD, and (f) PCB. Best viewed in color.

930 This reduces computational overhead, and substantially decreases reliance
931 on manual annotation.

932 Future research will focus on enhancing the efficiency and deployability
933 of the OneN framework in industrial scenarios. Specifically, we plan to fur-
934 ther investigate class imbalance across various anomaly detection tasks and
935 explore quantization techniques to enable deployment on low-power and em-
936 bedded hardware. Another promising direction involves distilling knowledge
937 into multiple compact variants by reducing network depth and patch res-
938 olution, thereby offering lightweight yet interpretable solutions suitable for
939 diverse edge devices.

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